

Verification of Statistical Seasonal Tropical Cyclone Forecast

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ABSTRACT

10 Seasonal hurricane forecasts are an important tool for hurricane prepared-
11 ness and planning before the start of a hurricane season. Each year, U.S.
12 forecasters predict the number of seasonal named storms, hurricanes, and ma-
13 jor hurricanes that will occur in the Atlantic Basin (including the Caribbean
14 Sea and the Gulf of Mexico), as well as in the North East Pacific. Statisti-
15 cal hurricane forecasts are probabilistic forecasts for the number of seasonal
16 named storms to form in a particular area, where the probability distributions
17 are estimated from past data. The available data record of reliable sources is
18 relatively short, which makes drawing conclusions rather difficult. To improve
19 forecasting and develop better hurricane preparedness strategies, forecasters
20 must assess the validity of forecasting methods and quantify their uncertainty.
21 This study proposes a verification procedure to be applied to statistical sea-
22 sonal hurricane forecasts that takes into account the probabilistic nature of the
23 forecast. The procedure is implemented in order to evaluate the impact (or the
24 lack thereof) of using two variable selection methods, using forecasted ENSO
25 indices, and to compare the skill of forecasts that use information up to March
26 versus up to May in the Atlantic Basin.

27 **1. Introduction**

28 Quantifying and characterizing the uncertainty in forecasts is essential for their proper statistical
29 interpretation and further utilization by public and private decision makers (government officials,
30 insurance companies, agriculture-based business, among others). Forecasters produce three types
31 of seasonal hurricane outlooks: statistical, dynamical, and a blend of both (Camargo et al. (2010)).
32 Whereas dynamical forecasts give a non-probabilistic prediction, which lacks an uncertainty char-
33 acterization, a statistical forecast gives a probabilistic measure, using historical data to construct a
34 statistical model and estimate a probability distribution of the quantity of interest. Statistical fore-
35 casts have been widely used to produce hurricane season outlooks (Gray et al. (1994)). Forecasts
36 are a result of many decisions such as which month-specific covariates to include, how to select
37 them, and what probability distribution to use. Thus, an evaluation of the impact of these decisions
38 when constructing a forecast is needed. This paper aims to provide a framework to validate and
39 evaluate the model and method decisions while taking into account the probabilistic nature of the
40 forecast, by using a probability distribution as opposed to using just a point estimate.

41 After the VI International Workshop on Tropical Cyclones (ITWC-VI) in 2006, the agreement
42 among forecast groups was “to develop guidelines for the development and validation of the tropi-
43 cal cyclone forecasts” (Camargo et al. (2010)). The World Meteorology Organization (WMO) has
44 only published suggested verification skill scores and very general guidelines for all long-range
45 forecasts (LRF) (WMO (2002)). Also, WMO encourages the use of probabilistic forecasts, given
46 that they suggest the use of proper scores (as defined in Gneiting and Katzfuss (2014)) to evaluate
47 all LRFs.

48 The website <http://www.bsc.es/ESS/seasonalhurricanepredictions/> (Caron and
49 Klotzbach (2016)) presents seventeen forecast groups that release their hurricane seasonal out-

50 look for the Atlantic Basin every year. Seven of them use statistical forecasts exclusively and are
51 presented in Table 1. Commonalities among all the groups with statistical forecasts are the use of
52 storm counts as the predictand and measures of sea surface temperatures and climate indices as
53 predictors.

54 Most of the literature on statistical seasonal hurricane forecasts have a section on verification,
55 where they evaluate their forecast based on methods like cross-validation (CV) or jackknife. For
56 example, Saunders and Lea (2005) use a 5-year block cross-validation hindcast, following the
57 recommendations from Elsner and Schmertmann (1994) and WMO (2002). They eliminate 5-
58 year blocks of observations at a time, then hindcast those values and compare them with the
59 observed ones using Spearman rank correlation. Leave-one-out cross-validation (LOOCV) and
60 ranked probability skill score are used by Xie et al. (2014) and Keith and Xie (2009) to compare
61 their forecast with climatology. Yan et al. (2015) also uses LOOCV, and calculate the root mean
62 square error and the ranked skill score for the same purpose.

63 Kozar et al. (2012) and Davis et al. (2015) use the data for two independent cross-validation
64 experiments to evaluate their forecast skill. Kozar et al. (2012) split the data first into two equal
65 parts and uses the first half to calibrate the model, then forecasts the second half. The second
66 experiment is a one-year validation methodology, where they predict the number of storms in one
67 year, using all previous data. For both experiments, they use the coefficient of determination R^2 ,
68 the coefficient of efficiency, and the reduction of error as scores. Davis et al. (2015) on the other
69 hand, divide the data set into two periods: 1950-1980 and 1981-2013 to test the robustness of
70 their forecast. In the first period they use future data to fit a model and predict past values, as a
71 sensitivity test, and for the second part they use only past data to forecast each year. They use mean
72 absolute error and root mean square error to compare their statistical model prediction capabilities
73 with respect to the climatology.

74 Research from Jagger and Elsner (2010), Lehmiller et al. (1997) and Klotzbach (2007) are not
75 included in Caron and Klotzbach (2016) as groups with statistical seasonal hurricane forecasts,
76 but they have proposed verification techniques for statistical forecasts in the literature. Elsner and
77 Jagger (2006) first use a Bayesian model to forecast and maximum *a posteriori* as hindcast skill,
78 and in a later paper they use 11-fold cross-validation to compare their consensus model with other
79 options in terms of mean square error, ranked probability and Brier (quadratic) score, as well as
80 the logarithmic score (Jagger and Elsner (2010)). Klotzbach (2007) uses hindcast cross-validation
81 and warns that the practice of evaluating hindcasts using future data to predict the past “should
82 only be used as an upper bound measure for skill”. In this case, R^2 and MSE are used to measure
83 the forecast skill. Lehmiller et al. (1997) provide a different perspective and use multivariate
84 discriminant analysis to forecast location and occurrence of storms in the Atlantic Basin. They use
85 proportion of correct forecasts in cross-validation to verify their forecasts.

86 An important part of constructing statistical forecasts is the variable selection method. Most
87 of the literature in statistical seasonal hurricane forecasts use a small set of covariates when con-
88 structing their statistical model (see for example Elsner and Jagger (2006), Davis et al. (2015)
89 and Keith and Xie (2009)). They select the covariates based on their expert opinion, either from
90 previous evidence of association or from scientific hypotheses. Xie et al. (2014) and Yan et al.
91 (2015) use the forward and backward approach, to perform variable selection in a relatively small
92 (9) set of covariates. Jagger and Elsner (2010) on the other hand, incorporate Bayesian model
93 averaging techniques as an alternative for variable selection, where they average over all possi-
94 ble models constructed using different combinations of five covariates. None of these studies take
95 into account all possible month-specific variables that have been shown to have an association with
96 tropical cyclones, mainly due to the curse of dimensionality, in which there are more covariates
97 than observations and thus, insufficient degrees of freedom to estimate the full model.

98 The main objective of this paper is to propose a detailed guideline to verify statistical seasonal
99 hurricane forecasts that takes into account only past data, and acknowledges its probabilistic na-
100 ture. In order to highlight its importance, the verification method is compared to other methods
101 that use hindcast methods without making the difference between the past and future data. Fur-
102 thermore, to illustrate the verification method, a set of forecasting models are constructed first and
103 then evaluated. Specifically, these models aim to predict the distribution of tropical storms (TS),
104 hurricanes (HR) and major hurricanes (MH) counts to form or pass through particular areas of the
105 Atlantic Basin during a specific hurricane season (1 June to 30 November). Moreover, the use of
106 LASSO and clustering as variable selection procedures to construct the forecasts is proposed and
107 the need of incorporating them into the cross-validation procedure is discussed. These variable
108 selection procedures for tropical cyclone forecast can handle a set of covariates larger than the
109 number of observations.

110 The rest of this paper is organized into four sections. Section 2 presents the definitions and
111 general notations for statistical seasonal hurricane forecasts. In section 3 the tropical cyclone data
112 and possible predictors for the analysis are presented, as well as a description of the methodology
113 used in the proposed verification procedure and the construction and variable selection of the
114 SHFs. Section 4 describes the numerical results in terms of selected predictors using the proposed
115 variable selection method as well as the corresponding model verification. Section 5 contains the
116 conclusions and discussion.

117 2. Definitions

118 a. Statistical Seasonal Hurricane Forecasts

119 Gneiting and Katzfuss (2014) define a probabilistic forecast as a “forecast in the form of a
120 probability distribution over future quantities or events.” There are several ways to represent a
121 probabilistic forecast, but Gneiting and Ranjan (2013) recommend to write it as a predictive cu-
122 mulative distribution function (CDF), given its “unified treatment of all real-valued predictands.”
123 These real-valued predictands can be density forecasts, mixed discrete-continuous predictive dis-
124 tributions, probability mass functions for count data, and probability forecast of a dichotomous
125 event. The forecast F can be constructed without observed data, i.e. assuming a probability dis-
126 tribution and fixed parameters, or using observed data to estimate the parameters of a probability
127 distribution. In this article, the latter is defined as a statistical forecast.

128 A statistical seasonal hurricane forecast (SHF) is defined as a probabilistic forecast for the total
129 counts of tropical cyclones to form in a particular area, where the probability distributions are esti-
130 mated from past data. According to Klotzbach et al. (2010) and Camargo et al. (2007) most of the
131 statistical seasonal hurricane forecasts use regression models. The main difference between them
132 is the response that is used. Saunders and Lea (2005) use the accumulated cyclonic energy (ACE)
133 as a continuous response, while all other authors use the number of tropical cyclones (tropical
134 storms, hurricanes, major hurricanes, landfalling storms) as a discrete response. In the latter case,
135 the distribution assumed is discrete, specifically, a probability mass function for count data, and it
136 is represented using its CDF value.

137 Consider n years of data $\{y_i, x_{i1}, \dots, x_{ip}\}$, where y_i is a storm count in year i , and x_{i1}, \dots, x_{ip}
138 are covariate values (e.g. sea surface temperature indices in year i). In the forecast literature,
139 climatology is used as a reference to evaluate the efficacy of various forecast methods. In this

140 paper, climatology is defined in two ways: (1) $\hat{F}_1 = \text{Poisson}(\bar{y})$, where $\bar{y} = \sum_{i=1}^n y_i/n$, and (2) \hat{F}_2
 141 as the empirical CDF of y_1, \dots, y_n . The second option is useful for shedding some light on the
 142 correctness of the Poisson distribution assumption. Climatology forecasts do not make use of
 143 covariates that vary from year to year. In order to incorporate these covariates, the mean storm
 144 count is modeled as

$$\log \mu_i = \beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^p x_{ij} \beta_j.$$

145 The dataset can be used to provide parameter estimates $\hat{\beta}_0, \dots, \hat{\beta}_p$, and then the forecast distribu-
 146 tion for year $n + 1$ is simply $F_3 = \text{Poisson}(\hat{\mu}_{n+1})$, where

$$\log \hat{\mu}_{n+1} = \hat{\beta}_0 + \sum_{j=1}^p x_{n+1,j} \hat{\beta}_j$$

147 When there are many covariates available, it is often preferred to set some of the parameter es-
 148 timates exactly to zero, effectively eliminating certain covariates from affecting the forecast. A
 149 careful study of this variable selection procedure is one of the contributions of this paper.

150 Compared to other seasonal hurricane forecasts like the dynamical or blended, statistical fore-
 151 casts have the advantage of being extremely fast to compute, simple to implement and interpret,
 152 and also that they provide a measure of variability, due to their probabilistic nature.

153 *b. Verification Methods for Statistical Seasonal Hurricane Forecasts*

154 According to Wilks (2005) a “forecast verification involves measures of the relationship between
 155 a forecast or a set of forecasts, and the corresponding observation(s) of the predictand.” Given the
 156 nature of the statistical model, using the same data to construct the statistical forecast and also
 157 verify it, will cause underestimation of errors (James et al. (2013)). Therefore, when proposing a
 158 verification method for a statistical forecast, there are two procedures that need to be addressed:
 159 first, how to separate the data into training and test sets and thus calculate and evaluate the forecast

160 using independent data, and second, how to measure the relationship between the forecast and the
161 observed values. The definitions for each of the procedures are as follows.

162 1) SCORING RULES

163 A scoring rule function measures the accuracy of probabilistic predictions. According to Gneiting
164 and Katzfuss (2014), a scoring rule $S(F,y)$ assigns a numerical score to each pair of (F,y) ,
165 where F represents a probabilistic forecast and y is the realized value. In the meteorology liter-
166 ature, many authors rely on the root mean squared error or simply on a binary measure of the
167 confidence interval including or not the real value as distance measures (e.g. hit rate, linear error
168 probability space, probability of detection, false alarm rate, among others). The problem with a
169 binary measure in this case, is that ignores the forecast variability.

170 Gneiting and Katzfuss (2014) define a scoring rule to be proper if the expected score of an
171 observation drawn from the distribution G is minimized using the probabilistic forecast G , rather
172 than any other $F \neq G$. In other words, if S is a proper scoring rule, and if observations Y are
173 drawn from G , and our forecast distribution is F , then $E(S(G,Y)) \leq E(S(F,Y))$. The scoring rule
174 is strictly proper if the inequality is strict whenever $F \neq G$.

175 WMO (2002) recommends the relative operating characteristic curve (ROC) skill score, ranked
176 probability skill score (RPSS) or likelihood skill scores (Harte and Vere-Jones (2005)) to validate
177 statistical seasonal hurricane forecast, depending on the nature of the predictand. The ROC skill
178 score is only useful for evaluating binary outcomes. RPSS and the likelihood skill score have the
179 ranked probability score and the logarithmic score (LS) as their associated scoring rules, respec-
180 tively. The LS is a proper scoring rule (Gneiting and Katzfuss (2014)), and the ranked probability
181 has a modified version called continuous ranked probability score for evaluating probabilistic fore-
182 casts, which is also a proper scoring rule (Gneiting and Katzfuss (2014)).

183 The LS has the advantage of acknowledging the probabilistic nature of the forecast and of being
 184 a proper score, compared to MSE, MAE and other scalar accuracy measures. Compared to the
 185 continuous ranked probability score the LS is simpler to calculate, and it is recommended for
 186 evaluating forecasts that are generated by probabilistic models, given its relationship with the
 187 likelihood ratio and the concept of Bayes factors (Gneiting and Raftery (2007)).

188 The logarithmic score $LS(F, y)$ is used in this study to compare the forecast value from F with
 189 the observed value y_i , using the following formula:

$$LS(F, y_i) = -\log [F(y_i | \hat{\mu}_{i-1}) - F(y_i - 1 | \hat{\mu}_{i-1})] \quad (1)$$

190 where $\hat{\mu}_{i-1}$ is the estimated parameter calculated using the previous $i - 1$ observations. The like-
 191 lihood skill score is defined as:

$$\bar{H} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n [LS(\hat{F}, y_i) - LS(F, y_i)] \quad (2)$$

192 where \hat{F} is the climatology defined in the previous section. The likelihood skill score recom-
 193 mended by the WMO is defined as $\tilde{p} = \exp(\bar{H})$ and is equivalent to the log probability gain (see
 194 entropy score in Harte and Vere-Jones (2005)). Positive values of H or in the same way values of
 195 \tilde{p} greater than 1 indicate superior skill than climatology for model F .

196 2) CROSS-VALIDATION AND SLIDING WINDOW CROSS-VALIDATION

197 In a data-rich situation, James et al. (2013) recommended to split the observed data into training,
 198 validation and testing sets, to be able to characterize the forecast uncertainty properly. The same
 199 authors encourage the use of “efficient sample re-use, such as cross-validation or bootstrap” in
 200 cases where the data is limited. Cross-validation is a method that partitions a sample of data into
 201 complementary subsets, one to fit the model and the other to test it. These partitions can be done
 202 by splitting the data into K equal-sized parts (K-fold) to fit the model using $K - 1$ parts of the

203 data, and calculate and test the forecast using the remaining part. The procedure is repeated for
204 $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$ to have K estimates of an evaluation measure. When K is equal to the sample size,
205 the cross-validation is called leave-one-out cross-validation (LOOCV). In all cases the final goal
206 is to have several repetitions of the estimated measure, to construct an empirical distribution and
207 hence an approximation of its variability.

208 Elsner and Schmertmann (1994) describe cross-validation for assessing forecast skill and warn
209 about two common errors: “false cross-validation” and “serial correlation.” The first one refers
210 to the use of information from the test set when fitting the model, and the second refers to the
211 presence of observations in the training data set that are “especially informative about the omitted
212 predictand, but unavailable in a real forecast situation” (Elsner and Schmertmann (1994)). The
213 first problem commonly arises when performing variable selection procedures in a preliminary
214 process that uses all the data to choose a final model, and then partition the data to validate the
215 final model. The second problem might be present when using k -fold CV, since it is possible that
216 the use of future years can contribute to a better forecast when in reality the information will not
217 be available in a real forecast situation.

218 Also, since calculating a scoring rule or any other statistic using only one sample is not useful to
219 quantify uncertainty, a verification method needs not only to have a training set and a testing set,
220 but also repetitions of said estimation. A verification process that uses a sliding window creates
221 the repetitions needed and avoids the common cross-validation errors, since the method respects
222 the temporal order nature of the data.

223 In a sliding window cross-validation (SWCV), each window is composed by n_T training obser-
224 vations (years) and a $n_E = 1$ testing observation (year). The i th testing set is $(y_i, x_{i1}, \dots, x_{ip})$, with
225 training set $(y_{i-n_T}, x_{i-n_T,1}, \dots, x_{i-n_T,p}), \dots, (y_{i-1}, x_{i-1,1}, \dots, x_{i-1,p})$. Thus, the training set for each
226 observation consists of the data in the immediately preceding n_T years, as shown in Figure 1. The

227 model is fitted using n_T years and the scoring rule is calculated using the forecast of the n_E obser-
228 vation in each window of the data. The window incrementally advances across all possible years
229 and, at each new year, the scoring rule is calculated using the forecast from the model constructed
230 using n_T training observations. The procedure is repeated for $i = 1, \dots, w$. In each window, a fore-
231 cast value from F_i is compared with the observed value y_i using $S(F_i, y_i)$. In this way, a statistical
232 seasonal hurricane forecast can be constructed using each window of data and evaluated with the
233 subsequent year.

234 Moving window cross-validation allows repeating the exercise w times, each of them with the
235 same sample size, using the historical data. SWCV respects the chronological order of the data and
236 gives a more realistic approximation of the true forecast procedure. On the other hand, it implies
237 to reduce the sample size, since the data is split into groups of smaller windows. Nevertheless, the
238 advantages of having several samples to measure variability and having realistic forecast scenarios
239 can overcome the small sample size disadvantage in this case. In the next section, the data and
240 specific methods used in this paper are presented.

241 **3. Application to TC in the Atlantic Basin**

242 The goal is to compare two climatology definitions and two cross-validation types, and then
243 use the best combination to evaluate several model options for statistical seasonal hurricane fore-
244 casts, using tropical storms in the Atlantic Basin data. To illustrate the verification method, a set
245 of forecasting models are constructed first and then evaluated in terms of the following model-
246 ing decisions: type of variable selection method, Outlook release month and group of variables
247 included.

248 *a. Data*

249 The historical tropical cyclone (TC) counts are obtained from the National Hurricane Cen-
250 ter (NHC) HURDAT best-track data map available at: [http://www.nhc.noaa.gov/pastall.](http://www.nhc.noaa.gov/pastall.shtml)
251 [shtml](http://www.nhc.noaa.gov/pastall.shtml). TC counts are determined by region and then further categorized by the peak strength
252 within each region according to the Saffir-Simpson hurricane wind scale. The three regions are
253 the Atlantic Ocean, the Caribbean Sea, and the Gulf of Mexico (Figure 2). The Atlantic Ocean
254 regions (ATL) stands for the whole Atlantic TC basin. The Caribbean Sea region (CAR) is en-
255 closed by the West Indies and the coast of Central America from the East coast of the Yucatan
256 Peninsula to Venezuela. The Gulf of Mexico region (GOM) is bordered by the Gulf Coast of the
257 United States (from the Southern tip of Florida to Texas) to Mexico and the Northern edge of the
258 Yucatan Peninsula and the Northwestern coast of Cuba. This best track data for the Atlantic basin
259 contains data since 1851. However, only data after 1951 are used in this analysis because of the
260 large uncertainties due to non reliable sources in the earlier data (Xie et al. (2014)). Subtropical
261 and extra-tropical storms, as well as storms outside of the 1 June-31 November hurricane season,
262 are filtered out. In total, there are 65-years (1951-2015) of observations for all variables, with a
263 total of 698 tropical cyclones.

264 Various climate factors are considered as predictors of TC counts for an upcoming hurricane
265 season. These candidate predictors include SST-related climate indices, El Niño Southern Oscilla-
266 tion (ENSO) related indices, atmospheric and teleconnection indices, as well as parameters in the
267 Main Development Region (MDR) for Atlantic hurricanes.

268 NOAA Earth System Research Laboratory's Physical Division ([http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/](http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/climateindices/list)
269 [psd/data/climateindices/list](http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/climateindices/list)) compiles the information from NOAA sources, including
270 Climate Prediction Center and Atlantic Oceanographic and Meteorological Laboratory. Atlantic

271 SST-related climate indices such as AO (Atlantic Oscillation), NAO (Northern Atlantic Oscilla-
272 tion), AMM (Atlantic Meridional Mode), AMO (Atlantic Multi-decadal Oscillation), TNA (Trop-
273 ical Northern Atlantic), TSA (Tropical Southern Atlantic) and DM (Atlantic Dipole Mode) are
274 included as possible predictors and collected from such sources.

275 Pacific SST-related climate indices are also included. PNA (Pacific North American Index),
276 WP (Pacific Warm-pool), WHWP (Western Hemisphere Warm Pool), SOI (Southern Oscillation
277 Index), EPO (East Pacific/North Pacific Oscillation), and PDO (Pacific Decadal Oscillation) are
278 listed in the aforementioned sources. Also, a group of SST indices from the correspondent Niño
279 regions is listed (NINO12, NINO34, NINO3, NINO4), MEI (Multivariate ENSO Index), CENSO
280 (Bivariate ENSO) and TNI (Trans-Niño Index). Other indices from the same sources are Solar
281 Flux and QBO (Quasi-Biennial Oscillation).

282 Several measures from the main development region (MDR, 10-20N, 80-20W) are included
283 as climate indices. These includes monthly averaged sea-level pressure (MDRSLP), SST
284 (MDRSST), and vertical wind shear (MDRVWS, wind shear between 200 and 850 mb). Also,
285 200 and 850 mb pressure level u and v wind (m/s) measures from the same region are included
286 (MDRU200, MDRU850, MDRV200, and MDRV850). All the MDR indices are derived from the
287 NCEP/NCAR Reanalysis I dataset by <http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/timeseries/>

288 Global (GGST), north-hemisphere (NGST), and south-hemisphere (SGST) monthly Land-
289 Surface Air and Sea-Surface Water Temperature Anomalies, based on the GISS Surface Tem-
290 perature Analysis (GISTEMP), are also used as candidate predictors. Data is obtained from GISS
291 (NASA) and is available from <http://data.giss.nasa.gov/>.

292 The surface latent heat flux (LHF) derived from the NCEP/NCAR reanalysis data is used to
293 compute Empirical Orthogonal Functions (EOFs). Winter data is used to calculate anomalies
294 and then construct EOFs. In total 34 indices with monthly measures per year are considered

295 as predictors. Since many of these variables are almost perfectly correlated with each other, a
296 pre-processing dendrogram analysis was carried to define a list of 10 possible covariates in each
297 window. Definitions and more specific sources for all indices can be found in Appendix 1.

298 *b. Verification Procedure*

299 The data is divided into 35 windows to use the sliding windows procedure described in Section
300 2. The number of windows and the size of each of them is calculated in a way that the sample size
301 for both windows and years within windows is not smaller than 30. A small sensitivity study was
302 performed to see how the window size changed the results, with no significant change.

303 The first step is to construct the model using data from 1951-1980, and then forecast 1981. Since
304 there are 65 years in total, the procedure can be repeated 35 times, to forecast 2015 using the last
305 window of data, as shown in Figure 1. The log score ($LS(F, y)$) is calculated using the formula
306 specified in Equation 1 and then \bar{H} is calculated with the number of windows as the sample size n .

307 The statistical forecast F with higher \bar{H} will be then chosen to forecast 2016. In order to illustrate
308 the verification method, a set of the forecasting models are constructed first and then evaluated
309 using the proposed method. Leave-one-out cross-validation is used as a comparison since it is the
310 most commonly used method, and will be labeled from now on as:

- 311 • **SWCV**. Proposed sliding window cross-validation method, described in Section 2d.
- 312 • **RCV**. Regular LOOCV cross-validation is used as baseline comparison. Again, future data
313 is used to forecast the past.

314 All the standard error (SE) calculations were approximated using bootstrap with $B = 10000$
315 iterations. The bootstrap includes an implicit assumption of independent samples, which could be

316 violated in this application, so we also computed standard errors under an AR(1) model for the log
317 scores, and the results did not change significantly, so we used the bootstrap throughout.

318 The statistical forecasts estimate the distributions of the tropical storms (TS), hurricanes (HR)
319 and major hurricanes (MH) counts to form or pass through particular areas of the Atlantic Basin
320 during a hurricane season (1 June to 30 November). In the next section, the SHF construction and
321 variable selection procedure is presented.

322 *c. SHFs Construction and Variable Selection*

323 A generalized linear model LASSO regularization is used (James et al. (2013)). The model as-
324 sumes that the logarithm of the intensity parameter μ is linearly related to the climate indices, and
325 performs a variable selection procedure using a shrinkage parameter, to identify the combination
326 of indices that has the best predictive ability. LASSO is useful to handle cases where there are
327 more covariates than observations. In this case, LASSO is especially useful since 35 covariates
328 multiplied by the number of months observed is in many cases greater than the number of years
329 observed. Nevertheless, depending on the window of data, the correlation between two covariates
330 can be almost perfect, in which case LASSO has limitations. Hence, a hierarchical clustering al-
331 gorithm (hclust, from R Core Team (2016)) is applied before applying LASSO in each window, to
332 select one variable for each of the $k = 10$ clusters constructed using distances from the covariates
333 correlation matrix. The number of cluster is selected to have a big enough collection of variables
334 that could provide enough information, and a small enough number of variables to have enough
335 residual degrees of freedom left. Figure 3 presents the results of a cluster analysis with all 65
336 years, as an example. The algorithm selects 10 clusters and then chooses the variable with high-
337 est correlation with the response in each cluster, in each window separately. Hastie et al. (2009)
338 highlights the importance of incorporating the complete algorithm, including variable selection,

339 in cross-validation, arguing that “in a multistep modeling procedure, cross-validation must be ap-
340 plied to the entire sequence of modeling steps.” (p.246). Therefore, both the cluster and LASSO
341 procedures are applied in each window.

342 Nine sets of month-specific predictors were used to construct three different model options for
343 the forecasts. These sets are a combination of time domains for the climate indices (covariates)
344 and groups of covariates: Core group, NINO group and LHF group, with the objective of having
345 different scenarios for the outlook release date (March, May or March with ENSO JAS (July,
346 August, September)). The NINO group is composed by all ENSO related climate indices, the
347 LHF group includes the EOFs constructed using LHF winter data, and the Core group contains
348 all other indices (see Table 2). The goal in here is to investigate whether or not it is worth to use
349 forecasted data (March vs March with ENSO) and/or if a forecast released at the beginning of the
350 season is better than one released in April using forecasted data (May vs March ENSO).

351 In summary, the following models are used to make a comparison using the verification method,
352 for each response:

353 F_{1X} : March Outlook using core variables (F_{1B}), core and NINO variables (F_{1N}), or core, NINO
354 and LHF variables (F_{1L}). The model is constructed using data from January and February.
355 This outlook can be ready by April 1st, when the first forecast is released.

356 F_{2X} : May Outlook using core variables (F_{2B}), core and NINO variables (F_{2N}), or core, NINO and
357 LHF variables (F_{2L}). The model is constructed using data from January to April. This outlook
358 can be ready by June 1st, when the forecast is updated at the beginning of the season.

359 F_{3X} : March Outlook and ENSO JAS using core variables (F_{3B}), core and NINO variables (F_{3N}),
360 or core, NINO and LHF variables (F_{3L}). The model is constructed using data from January
361 and February, plus the ENSO values from July, August, and September. This model uses

362 future data since the NINO information is not available until the beginning of the hurricane
 363 season, but it is used to evaluate the possibility of equating the future NINO values' forecast
 364 skill with other variables. This outlook can be ready by April 1st, when the first forecast is
 365 released.

366 For each of the training sets $\{y_i, x_{i1}, \dots, x_{ip}\}_1^n$, a Poisson distribution with intensity parameter μ_i
 367 was used to model the counts: $Y_i \sim \text{Poisson}(\mu_i)$ with: $\log(\mu_i) = \beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^p x_{ij}\beta_j$. Here, it is of
 368 interest to minimize the following function (objective function):

$$\min_{\beta_0, \beta} -\frac{1}{N} \ell(\beta|X, Y) + \alpha \left(\sum_{j=1}^p |\beta_j| \right)$$

369 where $\ell(\beta|X, Y)$ is the likelihood function,

$$\ell(\beta|X, Y) = \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i(\beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^p x_{ij}\beta_j) - \exp(\beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^p x_{ij}\beta_j))$$

370 and α is the LASSO shrinkage parameter and β_0 is the intercept; β_j and index j are the regression
 371 coefficients and the selected indices, respectively, which are specific to each region and strength
 372 category. All covariates are scaled based on the correspondent window values.

373 For clarity, the procedure can be described in the following steps (see also Figure 4) :

- 374 1. Divide the data into w windows, depending on the cross-validation method ($w = 35$ for
 375 SWCV or no windows for RCV).
- 376 2. In each window, construct a model: select 10 primary covariates using a cluster analysis and
 377 apply LASSO using the 10 covariates in each window.
- 378 3. Calculate LS .
- 379 4. Compare scores against climatology (\hat{F}_1 and \hat{F}_2) using \bar{H} .

380 All calculations are done using $\alpha = 0.05$, and thus 95% confidence interval are presented in
 381 all cases. All the analysis were done using R (R Core Team (2016)), and the code needed to

382 implement the verification method with or without the variable selection procedure is presented in
383 the supplementary material.

384 **4. Results**

385 *a. Selected Predictors*

386 Both the cluster and LASSO are used to select predictors for each of the forecasts F . It is
387 important to highlight that the models might select different predictors in each window since the
388 idea is to construct and test the model with different subsets of data (in each window). For that
389 reason, a good summary of the most important predictors is a count of how many times a variable
390 was selected for a specific F and response. The results are presented as the most frequently
391 selected variables using the cluster, and also using LASSO.

392 Table 3 presents the five most selected predictors using the LASSO models with SWCV method
393 in each of the F for the Atlantic Basin. February EPO, MDRSLP, MDRV200, and TSA are in all
394 models of the March Outlook. May Outlook also includes February MDRSLP and incorporates
395 March TSA, April NGST, and February TNA. ENSO JAS Outlooks include NINO12 from August
396 in F_{3B} , F_{3N} and F_{3L} as one of the most commonly selected predictors. Figure 5, shows a tile plot
397 for each response, with the percentage of times a predictor is selected using the cluster analysis
398 and the SWCV method. In each plot, the twenty variables that were selected the highest number
399 of times are presented for each response.

400 Figure 5 show the percentage of times a predictor is selected using cluster models with SWCV
401 method. May Outlook Models (F_{2B} , F_{2N} , F_{2L}) tend to select different variables than the March Out-
402 look and ENSO JAS models, in all responses. The variables highlighted with two black vertical
403 lines, represent the ENSO-related indices. Only the models for Atlantic tropical storms, hurricanes

404 and Gulf of Mexico major hurricanes select an ENSO-related index as a covariate, and within these
405 cases, these covariates get selected only in the ENSO JAS models (in 40% or more of the win-
406 dows). This result is important in terms of how variables like EPO from January or February are
407 selected more often and thus could contribute more with the model predictive skill. Furthermore,
408 most of the ENSO-related indices are selected in the ENSO JAS model, which suggests that the
409 important correlation between ENSO and number of storms is during the season, and not before
410 (January - May), or that at least the other ENSO variables correlate with the counts in a similar
411 way than the ENSO JAS indices.

412 Some predictors are selected consistently for some responses, across all F . For tropical cyclones
413 in the Atlantic Basin (TS, HU, and MH), February EPO, MDRSLP and MDRV200 are selected
414 throughout the models. The Caribbean region presents March TSA, February TNA and MDRSLP
415 in each model within the three possible CAR responses (TS, HU, MH). Finally, February EPO and
416 MDRSLP, along with August NINO12 are consistently selected in the models describing the Gulf
417 of Mexico tropical cyclones.

418 *b. Verification Results*

419 The objective of the verification procedure is to compare how well each of the forecasts predicted
420 the observed number of tropical storms, hurricanes and major hurricanes. The results are presented
421 as a comparison between the skill score \bar{H} of all the nine F s. Two climatologies (\hat{F}_1 and \hat{F}_2) are
422 analyzed to decide which climatology performs best. Then, the best option is applied to a total of
423 nine responses (TS, HU, MH for the three regions of the Atlantic Basin). There are three goals:
424 the first is to compare the models generated using LASSO and those generated using only cluster
425 for variable selection, the second one is to investigate whether or not is worth to use forecasted
426 ENSO data (March vs March with ENSO) and if a forecast released at the beginning of the season

427 is better than one released in April using forecasted ENSO data (May vs March ENSO). This will
428 evaluate how necessary the NINO forecast indices are in order to predict the number of storms
429 well. Lastly, the third goal is to compare the best model against climatology and see if there is a
430 significant improvement in the forecast.

431 With respect to the climatology scores measures, even though one can argue that the empirical
432 version is more robust to misspecification of the distribution and that it sets a higher standard to
433 compare model scores, it presents problems when the observed values are unique. Also, \hat{F}_1 is a
434 fair comparison given that all the models are constructed assuming a Poisson distribution. Thus,
435 to make sure the Poisson distribution is a realistic choice, a goodness of fit test is performed for all
436 models, using the residual deviance. The residual deviance is the difference between the deviance
437 of the current model and the maximum deviance of the ideal model where the predicted values
438 are identical to the observed. Therefore, if the residual difference is very small, the goodness of
439 fit test will not be significant, indicating that the model fits the data. The results are presented in
440 Table 4, where it is clear that the distribution is a good fit for all models. For this reason, \hat{F}_1 is
441 chosen to be the reference, but it is important to highlight that the use of the empirical distribution
442 is recommended in cases where several distribution choices are being compared.

443 When comparing two cross-validation options is important to highlight the need of having a
444 realistic validation method, that respects the temporal order of the observations. As mentioned
445 before, evaluating forecasts using RCV or any hindcast method that uses future data to evaluate
446 past forecast is not realistic, and thus not recommended in this case. Thus, since SWCV does not
447 use future data to evaluate past forecasts and gives slightly different results than using RCV (see
448 Figure5), it is chosen as the best cross-validation method, given that is considered a more realistic
449 scenario in terms of the forecasting procedure.

450 In section 3c, the procedure to construct and validate the models was outlined. The variable se-
451 lection procedure is explained in the second step, where a hierarchical clustering algorithm is used
452 to select 10 primary covariates before applying LASSO. Before drawing conclusions using the
453 LASSO models results, a comparison between the two sets of models with and without LASSO
454 was done, to follow the principle of using the simplest best model. Results are presented in Fig-
455 ure 6 where there are some cases where the LASSO model has superior skill compared to the
456 cluster model ($\bar{H} < 0$). Given that there is at least one case where LASSO is significantly better in
457 terms of skill, and no cases where $\bar{H} > 0$, the LASSO models are used to draw conclusions in this
458 case.

459 In order to identify those models that have a superior skill compared against climatology, another
460 comparison was done using $H = S(F_{i clim}, y_i) - S(F_{i LASSO}, y_i)$. In this case, mean values of H
461 that are positive and significantly different from zero, denote models with better skill compared
462 to climatology. Figure 7 shows how there is not one model that performs significantly better
463 than climatology. Thus, it is not meaningful to compare between models in each response. The
464 conclusions in this case would be very different if RCV and percentage of improvement of MSE
465 would have been used instead (Figure 5). As an example, if we calculate the mean percentage of
466 improvement $PE = (MSE_{clim} - MSE_F) / MSE_{clim}$ for each F in the Atlantic Basin tropical storms,
467 we would have obtained that F_{2B} had a 22.3% of improvement of skill compared to climatology.
468 If the conclusions were draw from here, most of the models for Atlantic Basin storms would be
469 more skillful than climatology.

470 It is worth to highlight that in case of finding a set of models with superior skill for one response,
471 the difference between scores of those models should be used as statistic, and its respective SE
472 should be calculated using $var(\bar{H})$ formula, correcting for multiple testing with the significance
473 level of α/c where c is the number of tests using the same full model.

474 *c. Use of method to verify past Outlooks*

475 The data for 1990-2015 Outlooks was collected from the Colorado State University group
476 (Klotzbach (2017)) since they are the only group with more than 10 years of forecasts. The data
477 was collected taking into account those Outlooks released in April of each year (1996-2015) and in
478 June for 1990-1995. The observed data and the climatology (average of the previous 40 years) are
479 collected and the score H is calculated with the formula $H = S(F_{i clim}, y_i) - S(F_{i model}, y_i)$ for year i ,
480 to then calculate its mean and SE using bootstrap with $B = 10000$. The results for the TS outlooks
481 ($CI = \{0.0252, 0.8464\}$) are positive and H is significantly different from zero, which means that
482 the CSU model for TS is superior to climatology. Nevertheless, the other two models for HU
483 ($CI = \{-0.4326, 0.3885\}$) and MH ($CI = \{-0.3208, 0.4963\}$) are not significantly different from
484 zero and thus, they are not significantly better in terms of forecast skill compared to climatology.

485 **5. Discussion**

486 A good and reliable verification procedure is essential due to the economic and societal implica-
487 tions of releasing a poor forecast. A simple, probabilistic, and more realistic approximation of the
488 true forecast verification method was presented, which incorporates a variable selection procedure
489 into the method, using sliding window cross-validation (SWCV) to resample the data and logarith-
490 mic score (LS) to measure the prediction skill of the statistical seasonal hurricane forecasts. It is
491 shown that LS for climatology gives similar results when using SWCV compared to LS using the
492 traditional RCV, but how when using the combination of RCV and MSE as a verification method
493 gives very different results as with the proposed method. In here it is argued that SWCV is a more
494 realistic way to verify forecasts, and that the SE correction for autocorrelation between windows
495 is needed. SWCV and LS take into account the probabilistic nature of the forecast and provides a
496 more realistic scenario, given that it does not use future data to evaluate past forecasts.

497 An important result is that using cluster analysis to preselect the variables in each model per-
498 forms almost as well as using LASSO in terms of their logarithmic score. The verification method
499 can be used to evaluate how necessary it is to use forecasted values and to evaluate any other
500 set of covariates, or modeling decisions. The article shows how to implement the procedure and
501 how to select possible variables from a set of covariates in the seasonal hurricane forecast context.
502 This procedure – and the code available in the supplementary material, provides a way to quantify
503 and characterize the uncertainty in seasonal hurricane forecasts, to be used with any other set of
504 covariates.

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510 APPENDIX A

511 **Definition of Climate Indices**

- 512 • AMM (Atlantic Meridional Mode): The result of a maximum covariance analysis of SSTs and the zonal and meridional
513 winds over the region 21S-32N, 74W-15E. This index is obtained from [http://sahale.aos.wisc.edu:4080/MModes/
514 Data/AMM.txt](http://sahale.aos.wisc.edu:4080/MModes/Data/AMM.txt).
- 515 • AMO (Atlantic Multi-decadal Oscillation): An index based on North Atlantic SSTs. This index is obtained from [http:
516 //www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/correlation/amon.us.data](http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/correlation/amon.us.data)www.esrl.noaa.gov.
- 517 • TNA (Tropical Northern Atlantic): Anomaly of the average of the monthly SST from 5.5N to 23.5N and 15W to 57.5W.
518 This index is obtained from <http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/correlation/tna.data>www.esrl.noaa.gov.

- 519 • TSA (Tropical Southern Atlantic): Anomaly of the average of the monthly SST from 0-20S and 10E-30W. This index is
520 obtained from <http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/correlation/tsa.data>www.esrl.noaa.gov.
- 521 • DM (Atlantic Dipole Mode): The difference between TNA and TSA SSTs.
- 522 • WHWP (Western Hemisphere Warm Pool): Monthly anomaly of the ocean surface area warmer than 28.5°C in the Atlantic
523 and eastern North Pacific. This index is obtained from <http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/correlation/whwp>.
524 [data](http://www.esrl.noaa.gov)www.esrl.noaa.gov.
- 525 • GGST, NGST, and SGST: Global, north-hemisphere, and south-hemisphere monthly Land-Surface Air and Sea-Surface Wa-
526 ter Temperature Anomalies based on the GISS Surface Temperature Analysis (GISTEMP). Data is obtained from <http://>
527 data.giss.nasa.gov/gistemp/taledata_v3/GLB.Ts.txtdata.giss.nasa.gov/gistemp, [http://data.giss.nasa.](http://data.giss.nasa.gov/gistemp/taledata_v3/NH.Ts.txt)
528 [gov/gistemp/taledata_v3/NH.Ts.txt](http://data.giss.nasa.gov/gistemp/taledata_v3/NH.Ts.txt)data.giss.nasa.gov/gistemp and [http://data.giss.nasa.gov/gistemp/](http://data.giss.nasa.gov/gistemp/taledata_v3/SH.Ts.txt)
529 [taledata_v3/SH.Ts.txt](http://data.giss.nasa.gov/gistemp/taledata_v3/SH.Ts.txt)data.giss.nasa.gov/gistemp.
- 530 • NINO12: SST index in the Nino1+2 region. This index is obtained from [http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/](http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/correlation/nina1)
531 [psd/data/correlation/nina1](http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/correlation/nina1).[data](http://www.esrl.noaa.gov)www.esrl.noaa.gov. To represent ENSO impacts, NINO12 values for the
532 July/August/September average during the hurricane season were used in building the model. And the forecast values
533 for NINO12 obtained from the National Center for Environmental Protection (NCEP) coupled forecast system (CFS) model
534 were used for forecasts of the upcoming hurricane season from 1 June 31 November 2016.
- 535 • SOI (Southern Oscillation Index): This index is obtained from <http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/correlation/>
536 [soi](http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/correlation/soi).[data](http://www.esrl.noaa.gov)www.esrl.noaa.gov.
- 537 • NAO (Northern Atlantic Oscillation): This index is obtained from <http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/>
538 [correlation/nao](http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/correlation/nao).[data](http://www.esrl.noaa.gov)www.esrl.noaa.gov.
- 539 • EPO (East Pacific/North Pacific Oscillation): This index is obtained from <http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/>
540 [correlation/epo](http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/correlation/epo).[data](http://www.esrl.noaa.gov)www.esrl.noaa.gov.
- 541 • PNA (Pacific North American Index): This index is obtained from <http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/>
542 [correlation/pna](http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/correlation/pna).[data](http://www.esrl.noaa.gov)www.esrl.noaa.gov.

- 543 • AO (Arctic Oscillation): This index is obtained from [http://www.cpc.ncep.noaa.gov/products/precip/CWlink/
544 daily_ao_index/monthly.ao.index.b50.current.ascii.tablewww.cpc.ncep.noaa.gov](http://www.cpc.ncep.noaa.gov/products/precip/CWlink/daily_ao_index/monthly.ao.index.b50.current.ascii.tablewww.cpc.ncep.noaa.gov).
- 545 • QBO (Quasi-Biennial Oscillation): This index is obtained from [http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/correlation/
546 qbo.datawww.esrl.noaa.gov](http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/data/correlation/qbo.datawww.esrl.noaa.gov).
- 547 • SFI (Solar Flux): observed monthly solar flux (10.7cm) at Ottawa/Penticton. Data available from [ftp://ftp.ngdc.
548 noaa.gov/STP/space-weather/solar-data/solar-features/solar-radio/noontime-flux/penticton/
549 penticton_observed/listings/listing_drao_noontime-flux-observed_monthly.txtwww.ngdc.noaa.gov](ftp://ftp.ngdc.noaa.gov/STP/space-weather/solar-data/solar-features/solar-radio/noontime-flux/penticton/penticton_observed/listings/listing_drao_noontime-flux-observed_monthly.txtwww.ngdc.noaa.gov).
- 550 • MDRSLP, MDRSST, MDRVWS: Monthly averaged sea-level pressure (MDRSLP), SST (MDRSST), and vertical wind
551 shear (MDRVWS, wind shear between 200 and 850 mb), over the main development region (MDR, 10-20N, 80-20W).
552 Data derived from the NCEP/NCAR Reanalysis I dataset by [http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/cgi-bin/data/
553 timeseries/timeseries.pl?ntype=1&var=OLR&level=2000&lat1=20&lat2=10&lon1=-80&lon2=-20&iseas=
554 0&mon1=0&mon2=0&iarea=0&typeout=1&Submit=Create+Timeserieswww.esrl.noaa.gov](http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/cgi-bin/data/timeseries/timeseries.pl?ntype=1&var=OLR&level=2000&lat1=20&lat2=10&lon1=-80&lon2=-20&iseas=0&mon1=0&mon2=0&iarea=0&typeout=1&Submit=Create+Timeserieswww.esrl.noaa.gov).

555 APPENDIX B

556 **Figures B1 and B2**

557 **References**

- 558 Camargo, S. J., A. H. Sobel, A. G. Barnston, and P. J. Klotzbach, 2010: The Influence of Natural
559 Climate Variability on Tropical Cyclones, and Seasonal Forecasts of Tropical Cyclone Activity.
560 *Global Perspectives on Tropical Cyclones, from Science to Mitigation*, J. C. Kepert, and J.D.,
561 Eds., chap. 11, 325–360, doi:10.1142/9789814293488_0011.
- 562 Caron, L.-P., and P. Klotzbach, 2016: Seasonal Hurricane Predictions. URL [http://www.bsc.es/
563 ESS/seasonalhurricanepredictions/](http://www.bsc.es/ESS/seasonalhurricanepredictions/), accessed: 2016-09-10.

564 Davis, K., X. Zeng, and E. A. Ritchie, 2015: A New Statistical Model for Predicting Seasonal
565 North Atlantic Hurricane Activity. *Weather and Forecasting*, **30** (3), 730–741, doi:10.1175/
566 WAF-D-14-00156.1.

567 Elsner, J., and C. Schmertmann, 1994: Assessing forecast skill through cross-validation. *Weather*
568 *and Forecasting*, **9**, 619–624.

569 Elsner, J. B., and T. H. Jagger, 2006: Prediction Models for Annual U.S. Hurricane Counts. *Jour-*
570 *nal of Climate*, **19** (12), 2935–2952, doi:10.1175/JCLI3729.1.

571 Gneiting, T., and M. Katzfuss, 2014: Probabilistic Forecasting. *Annual Review of Statistics and Its*
572 *Application*, **1** (1), 125–151, doi:10.1146/annurev-statistics-062713-085831.

573 Gneiting, T., and A. E. Raftery, 2007: Strictly Proper Scoring Rules, Prediction, and Esti-
574 mation. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, **102** (477), 359–378, doi:10.1198/
575 016214506000001437.

576 Gneiting, T., and R. Ranjan, 2013: Combining predictive distributions. *Electronic Journal of*
577 *Statistics*, **7**, 1747–1782, doi:10.1214/13-EJS823.

578 Gray, W. M., C. W. Landsea, P. W. Mielke, and K. J. Berry, 1994: Predicting Atlantic Basin
579 Seasonal Tropical Cyclone Activity by 1 June. *Weather and Forecasting*, **9** (1), 103–115, doi:
580 10.1175/1520-0434(1994)009<0103:PABSTC>2.0.CO;2.

581 Harte, D., and D. Vere-Jones, 2005: The Entropy Score and its Uses in Earthquake Forecasting.
582 *Pure and Applied Geophysics*, **162** (6-7), 1229–1253, doi:10.1007/s00024-004-2667-2, URL
583 <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00024-004-2667-2>.

584 Hastie, T., R. Tibshirani, and J. Friedman, 2009: *The Elements of Statistical Learning*. Springer
585 Series in Statistics, Springer New York, New York, NY, 220–246 pp., doi:10.1007/b94608, URL
586 <http://www.springerlink.com/index/10.1007/b94608>.

587 Jagger, T. H., and J. B. Elsner, 2010: A Consensus Model for Seasonal Hurricane Prediction.
588 *Journal of Climate*, **23** (22), 6090–6099, doi:10.1175/2010JCLI3686.1.

589 James, G., D. Witten, T. Hastie, and R. Tibshirani, 2013: *An Introduction to Statistical Learn-*
590 *ing*, Springer Texts in Statistics, Vol. 103. Springer New York, New York, NY, doi:10.1007/
591 978-1-4614-7138-7.

592 Keith, E., and L. Xie, 2009: Predicting Atlantic Tropical Cyclone Seasonal Activity in April.
593 *Weather and Forecasting*, **24** (2), 436–455, doi:10.1175/2008WAF2222139.1.

594 Klotzbach, P., 2017: Tropical Meteorology Project, CSU. Accessed: 2017-02-04, <http://tropical.colostate.edu/>.

596 Klotzbach, P. J., 2007: Revised Prediction of Seasonal Atlantic Basin Tropical Cyclone Activity
597 from 1 August. *Weather and Forecasting*, **22** (5), 937–949, doi:10.1175/WAF1045.1.

598 Kozar, M. E., M. E. Mann, S. J. Camargo, J. P. Kossin, and J. L. Evans, 2012: Stratified sta-
599 tistical models of North Atlantic basin-wide and regional tropical cyclone counts. *Journal of*
600 *Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, **117** (D18), n/a–n/a, doi:10.1029/2011JD017170.

601 Lehmiller, G. S., T. B. Kimberlain, and J. B. Elsner, 1997: Seasonal Prediction Models for North
602 Atlantic Basin Hurricane Location. *Monthly Weather Review*, **125** (8), 1780–1791, doi:10.1175/
603 1520-0493(1997)125<1780:SPMFNA>2.0.CO;2.

604 R Core Team, 2016: *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. Vienna, Austria,
605 R Foundation for Statistical Computing, URL <https://www.R-project.org/>.

- 606 Saunders, M. A., and A. S. Lea, 2005: Seasonal prediction of hurricane activity reaching the coast
607 of the United States. *Nature*, **434 (7036)**, 1005–1008, doi:10.1038/nature03454.
- 608 Wilks, D., 2005: *Statistical Methods in the Atmospheric Sciences*. International Geophysics, Else-
609 vier Science, URL https://books.google.com/books?id=_b4R9j2Iy7EC.
- 610 WMO, 2002: Standardized verification system (SVS) for long-range forecasts (LRF). *Manual on*
611 *the GDPS*, vol 1 ed., WMO, Geneva, chap. New Attach.
- 612 Xie, L., M. Alfaro-Córdoba, B. Liu, and M. Fuentes, 2014: 2014 Atlantic Tropical Cyclone
613 Outlook . Tech. rep., North Carolina State University, Raleigh. URL [http://cfdl.meas.ncsu.edu/
614 research/TCoutlook{_}2014.pdf](http://cfdl.meas.ncsu.edu/research/TCoutlook{_}2014.pdf).
- 615 Yan, T., L. J. Pietrafesa, D. A. Dickey, P. T. Gayes, and S. Bao, 2015: Seasonal prediction of
616 landfalling hurricanes along Eastern Seaboard of the United States. *International Journal of*
617 *Climatology*, **35 (9)**, 2647–2653, doi:10.1002/joc.4163.

618 **LIST OF TABLES**

619 **Table 1.** Forecast Groups that use statistical models exclusively, with their most recent
620 reference. 31

621 **Table 2.** Possible variables and time domains. 32

622 **Table 3.** Atlantic Basin Tropical Storms: Five most selected variables using LASSO
623 models, per F 33

624 **Table 4.** Median P-values for deviance goodness of fit test per response. Null hypothesis
625 is the Poisson models is a good fit for the data. Values marked with (*) mean
626 that the null hypothesis is rejected. 33

TABLE 1. Forecast Groups that use statistical models exclusively, with their most recent reference.

Forecast Group	Reference
Tropical Storm Risk (UCL)	Saunders and Lea (2005)
North Carolina State University	Xie et al. (2014), Keith and Xie (2009)
Coastal Carolina University	Yan et al. (2015)
Pennsylvania State University	Kozar et al. (2012)
University of Arizona	Davis et al. (2015)
Instituto Meteorológico Nacional (México)	N/A
Instituto Metereológico (Cuba)	N/A

TABLE 2. Possible variables and time domains.

Model	$F_1 = \text{March Outlook}$	$F_2 = \text{May Outlook}$	$F_3 = \text{March Outlook} + \text{JAS}$
Time Domain	2 months (Jan-Feb)	4 months (Jan-Feb + JAS)	4 months (Jan-April)
Core	AMM - AMO - AO - CENSO - DM - EPO - GGST MDRSST - MDRSLP - MDRU200 - MDRU850 - MDRV200 - MDRV850 - MDRVWS MEI - NAO - NGST - PDO - PNA - QBO - SFI - SGST - SOI - TNA - TSA - WHWP - WP		
NINO	NINO12 - NINO3 - NINO23 - NINO4		
LHF	LHF EOF WINTER (1 to 5)		

TABLE 3. Atlantic Basin Tropical Storms: Five most selected variables using LASSO models, per F .

F	First	Second	Third	Fourth	Fifth
F_{1B}	EPO02 (0.80)	MDRSLP02 (0.63)	MDRV20002 (0.54)	MDRSLP01 (0.49)	TSA02 (0.46)
F_{1N}	MDRSLP02 (0.80)	EPO02 (0.69)	AMM01 (0.57)	MDRV20002 (0.54)	TSA02 (0.49)
F_{1L}	EPO02 (0.66)	MDRSLP02 (0.60)	LHF.WIN3 (0.57)	MDRV20002 (0.49)	TNA02 (0.43)
F_{2B}	TSA03 (0.74)	TNA02 (0.54)	NGST04 (0.54)	MDRSLP02 (0.46)	MDRSST01(0.40)
F_{2N}	TSA03 (0.71)	NGST04 (0.57)	TNA02 (0.51)	MDRSLP02 (0.43)	NINO1202 (0.34)
F_{2L}	TSA03 (0.69)	TNA02 (0.57)	NGST04 (0.54)	MDRSLP02 (0.43)	NAO03 (0.40)
F_{3B}	EPO02 (0.80)	MDRV20002 (0.60)	MDRSLP02 (0.57)	NINO1208 (0.51)	TSA02 (0.46)
F_{3N}	MDRSLP02 (0.66)	EPO02 (0.63)	MDRV20002 (0.57)	NINO1208 (0.51)	AMM01 (0.51)
F_{3L}	EPO02 (0.66)	LHF.WIN3(0.6)	MDRSLP02 (0.54)	NINO1208 (0.51)	MDRV20002 (0.46)

627 TABLE 4. Median P-values for deviance goodness of fit test per response. Null hypothesis is the Poisson
 628 models is a good fit for the data. Values marked with (*) mean that the null hypothesis is rejected.

	F_{1B}	F_{1N}	F_{1L}	F_{2B}	F_{2N}	F_{2L}	F_{3B}	F_{3N}	F_{3L}
ATL TS	0.67	0.75	0.65	0.86	0.94	0.89	0.88	0.92	0.86
ATL HU	0.77	0.86	0.84	0.87	0.90	0.85	0.96	0.96	0.96
ATL MH	0.66	0.67	0.74	0.86	0.86	0.87	0.88	0.86	0.83
CAR TS	0.24	0.22	0.39	0.60	0.63	0.55	0.61	0.59	0.58
CAR HU	0.52	0.57	0.55	0.72	0.74	0.78	0.73	0.72	0.71
CAR MH	0.53	0.52	0.48	0.55	0.59	0.54	0.58	0.54	0.55
GOM TS	0.84	0.82	0.83	0.90	0.82	0.92	0.92	0.91	0.93
GOM HU	0.58	0.63	0.62	0.72	0.69	0.74	0.69	0.67	0.72
GOM MH	0.65	0.63	0.76	0.67	0.62	0.75	0.77	0.77	0.84

629 **LIST OF FIGURES**

630 **Fig. 1.** Sliding windows: Each row is a window w , displaying a training dataset ($n = n_T$) in gray,
631 test data ($n = n_E$) in dark gray and the final forecast year (2016) is displayed in black. 35

632 **Fig. 2.** Delimited Regions for the forecast 36

633 **Fig. 3.** Cluster analysis results for 33 possible covariates for all the data, as an example. Strong
634 dark tones represent perfect correlation. A dendrogram shows the grouped variables. 37

635 **Fig. 4.** Process Diagram for the Verification Method 38

636 **Fig. 5.** In the left column, the difference between climatology and MSE for Atlantic Basin tropical
637 storm models F are presented for each model, and for SWCV and RCV cross-validation.
638 The percentage of change between MSE for model F and climatology is presented on top
639 of each observation. Positive values mean that model F has lower MSE than climatology.
640 Right column present the results for $H = S(F_{i clim, y_i}) - S(F_{i LASSO, y_i})$ for each Atlantic Basin
641 tropical storm model and SWCV and RCV cross-validation. Intervals not overlapping zero
642 represent significant difference between LASSO and cluster models. Positive values indicate
643 superior skill of the cluster model, compared to LASSO model 39

644 **Fig. 6.** Mean $H = S(F_{i LASSO, y_i}) - S(F_{i cluster, y_i})$ by response. Intervals not overlapping zero rep-
645 resent significant difference between LASSO and cluster models. Positive values indicate
646 superior skill of the cluster model, compared to LASSO model. 40

647 **Fig. 7.** Mean $H = S(F_{i clim, y_i}) - S(F_{i LASSO, y_i})$ by response. Intervals not overlapping zero represent
648 significant difference between climatology and LASSO models. Positive values indicate
649 superior skill of LASSO model, compared to climatology. 41

650 **Fig. B1.** Percentage of times a Variable X is selected using LASSO models, per response and for
651 SWCV. In total, there are 35 windows (repetitions of the model). Nino variables are high-
652 lighted with bold lines. 42

653 **Fig. B2.** Percentage of times a Variable X is selected using cluster models, per response and for
654 SWCV. In total, there are 35 windows (repetitions of the model). Nino variables are high-
655 lighted with bold lines. 43

656 FIG. 1. Sliding windows: Each row is a window w , displaying a training dataset ($n = n_T$) in gray, test data
 657 ($n = n_E$) in dark gray and the final forecast year (2016) is displayed in black.

FIG. 2. Delimited Regions for the forecast

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 659 represent perfect correlation. A dendrogram shows the grouped variables.

FIG. 4. Process Diagram for the Verification Method

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 661 models F are presented for each model, and for SWCV and RCV cross-validation. The percentage of change
 662 between MSE for model F and climatology is presented on top of each observation. Positive values mean that
 663 model F has lower MSE than climatology. Right column present the results for $H = S(F_{i clim}, y_i) - S(F_{i LASSO}, y_i)$
 664 for each Atlantic Basin tropical storm model and SWCV and RCV cross-validation. Intervals not overlapping
 665 zero represent significant difference between LASSO and cluster models. Positive values indicate superior skill
 666 of the cluster model, compared to LASSO model

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 669 compared to LASSO model.

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 671 difference between climatology and LASSO models. Positive values indicate superior skill of LASSO model,
 672 compared to climatology.

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 676 total, there are 35 windows (repetitions of the model). Nino variables are highlighted with bold lines.